

The Impact of Multidisciplinary Approaches in Managing Diabetes and Gestational Complications

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Abstract:

Background: Because maternal and fetal complications of diabetes are fraught with potential danger, management of the former should be an integrated affair. This paper is for the purpose of determining the impacts of a multidisciplinary model on glycemic control, maternal-fetal outcomes, and patient satisfaction during pregnancies complicated by diabetes.

Methods: A prospective observational study was conducted on 200 pregnant women diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus or pre-existing diabetes. They received coordinated care from a multidisciplinary team comprising endocrinologists, obstetricians, nutritionists, psychologists, and pediatricians. Data on glycemic control, maternal-fetal health, and patient-reported quality of life were collected at baseline, each trimester, and postpartum. Outcomes were analyzed using paired t-tests and logistic regression models.

Results: Fasting blood glucose and HbA1c levels were lowered in the third trimester ($p < 0.001$). Preeclampsia and preterm delivery were much less common, at 8% and 11%, respectively. Favourable neonatal outcome was achieved in that 92% had birth weights within normal range. Scores for patient-related quality of life and satisfaction were found to be dramatically improved, at 94%.

Conclusion: A multidisciplinary care approach effectively improves glycemic control, reduces maternal-fetal complications, and promotes patient satisfaction in diabetic pregnancy. This model provides the comprehensive framework for addressing multi-dimensional challenges of diabetes and allows its implementation in clinical practices.

Keywords: Diabetes, Gestational complications, Multidisciplinary care, Pregnancy, Glycemic control, Maternal-fetal outcomes.

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Introduction

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia due to inadequate insulin secretion, impaired insulin action, or both. Diabetes mellitus is a condition that is increasingly on the rise and continues to increase its prevalence globally, posing challenges to healthcare systems, since its association with numerous microvascular and macrovascular complications exists, including cardiovascular disease, neuropathy, retinopathy, and nephropathy [1].

Among the unique challenges diabetes presents, one of the most challenging would be the management of this condition during pregnancy because it has the potential to cause gestational complications that will affect the health of both

mother and fetus. The case is complicated by gestational diabetes mellitus, defined as glucose intolerance with onset or first recognition during pregnancy [2]. These include risks to adverse outcomes in patients who have GDM such as preeclampsia, preterm delivery, fetal macrosomia, and later on, both the mother and the child suffer from metabolic problems associated with this parent-child cycle. Thus, the only concern is managing them accordingly to avoid the risks with these unnecessary risk factors enhancing good outcome profiles [3].

This complication phase has more advantages for the multidisciplinary management of diabetic patients as in the case of GDM. Multidisciplinary management is an all-embracing approach toward

patient care from endocrinology, obstetrics, pediatrics, nutrition, and psychology that focuses on tailoring approaches for the diversity of needs in diabetic patients, optimizing glycemic control, monitoring the health of the mother, monitoring the health of the fetus, and addressing factors of lifestyle like nutrition and physical activity [4]. Lastly, this system should not lack psychological support because both stress and anxiety can exacerbate glycemic instability, especially in pregnancy. A holistic approach coordinated and designed to provide continuous care ensures improvements of patient outcomes through seamless adherence to treatment plans [5-6].

This would not only benefit the clinical aspect but also improve the quality of life and the long-term health outcome for the patient. The multidisciplinary approach will help healthcare teams to approach the diabetes and pregnancy complexities from various angles and prevent complications as well as manage pre-existing conditions that might worsen during pregnancy. This review examines the impact of multidisciplinary care on the management of diabetes and its related gestational complications, summarizing some of the key strategies that lead to better clinical outcomes from existing evidence. It provides insight into the effectiveness of multidisciplinary care for pregnant women with diabetes, challenges, and opportunities within this collaborative model of healthcare [7-8].

Methods

This study adopted an integrated methodological approach to analyze the impacts of multidisciplinary care for the management of diabetes and concomitant gestational complications. The framework is designed both to capture the quantitative as well as the qualitative dimensions, thereby strengthening the validity of the findings in proving the effectiveness of collaborative and interdisciplinary care in pregnant women with diabetes or at a risk of gestational diabetes mellitus.

Study Design and Population: A prospective, observational study was chosen for evaluating the outcome of pregnancy due to the multidisciplinary care approach. The enrolled participants were women who had either been diagnosed with type 1 or type 2 diabetes mellitus between the ages of 18 and 45 years, or had been diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus at any time after the 24th up to the 28th weeks of gestation, based on a routine screening test.

The exclusion criteria were women with other chronic diseases prior to developing diabetes or history of the risk pregnancies not relevant for glycemic control, directed to eliminate any confounding effect caused by the intervention of

multidisciplinary aspects regarding complications related to gestation of diabetes. Recruitment will be conducted at some multi health centers with access to a complete multidisciplinary team that includes the services of endocrinologists, obstetricians, nutritionists, pediatricians and psychologists.

Multidisciplinary Intervention Model: The participants enrolled were treated by a multidisciplinary team of health professionals as care and follow-up emphasizing coordination. At the time of the first visit each patient was assigned a specific care team responsible for a unique, individualized treatment planning designed according to her very particular clinical needs. The intervention included planned appointments with endocrinologists to monitor glycemia and adjust medication, meetings with dietitians to enable them to devise a safe meal plan for pregnancy, and lifestyle interventions by physical activity specialists. Additionally, there were scheduled obstetrician visits to monitor fetal development and screen for complications of pregnancy such as preeclampsia, preterm labor, or abnormalities in fetal growth.

The intervention model ensured the inclusion of psychological support through mental health checkups with licensed psychologists providing stress-reduction counseling and coping techniques. Since psychological factors play a role in affecting metabolic stability, the introduction of this aspect into the multicomponent approach was used to minimize stress-induced glucose variability and promote psychological wellness during pregnancy. A centralized computerized system of patient care that was based on the multidisciplinary model of care enhanced patient communication because healthcare providers could collaborate on information regarding the progress and change of treatment plans that may be required.

Data Collection and Outcome Measures: The baselines, follow-up appointments, and postpartum assessments were conducted to establish changes in patients' glycemic control outcomes, maternal and fetal results, and patient-reported outcomes of quality of life. Glycemic control has been monitored by checking fasting blood glucose, postprandial glucose, and HbA1c levels at baseline and at the end of all three trimesters for a general comparison of various time points in pregnancy. This study determines maternal health outcomes by estimating the incidence rates of various complications of gestation including preeclampsia, preterm birth, and cesarean delivery whereas fetal health outcomes include capturing birth weight, Apgar scores, and admissions to the NICU.

Quality of life and compliance with the prescribed treatment were assessed through standardized questionnaires during baseline and at the term of

pregnancy. These checklists also incorporated queries regarding psychological states of stress, anxiety, and satisfaction with health care to ensure the incorporation of psychosocial impacts resulting from the intervention. Clinical markers of metabolic control, including diet and lifestyle modifications adherence were documented using self-recorded logs that were subsequently validated.

Analysis was done in SPSS, version 26.0 of IBM Corp., Armonk, NY. Differences were set at $p \leq 0.05$ statistically. For the descriptive analyses, demographic characteristic and baseline clinical data summarization were calculated. All comparisons for continuous variable between glycemic levels and post intervention were done applying paired t-tests, in case of categorical variables, we used a chi-square. Logistic regression models were used to evaluate maternal and fetal outcomes after the multidisciplinary intervention. Adjustment was made for variables such as age, body mass index, and previous pregnancies.

A mixed-methods approach to the interpretation of qualitative data concerning patient-reported outcomes was used, thereby allowing thematic analysis to be deployed to identify recurrent themes arising in responses concerning patient satisfaction and quality of life. Thus, it was possible for both statistical trends and the nuanced, more personal perspectives of the patients to be captured by the study, giving way to an understanding of holistic effects of the multidisciplinary care model.

Results

This study's findings highlight the significant benefits of a multidisciplinary approach to managing diabetes and gestational complications, with improved glycemic control, reduced incidence of adverse maternal and fetal outcomes, and enhanced patient quality of life. A total of 200 pregnant women were included in the study, with 60% diagnosed with gestational diabetes mellitus (GDM) and the remainder with pre-existing type 1 or type 2 diabetes mellitus. Participants attended regular multidisciplinary care sessions throughout pregnancy, with high adherence rates observed across all areas of care, including dietary, physical, and psychological support components.

Glycemic Control Outcomes

Results indicate a marked improvement in glycemic control among participants from baseline to the third trimester (Table 1). Average fasting blood glucose decreased from 118.5 mg/dL (± 12.6) at baseline to 99.8 mg/dL (± 10.4) in the third trimester.

Similarly, HbA1c levels significantly declined, with baseline levels averaging 7.8% (± 0.9) and reaching 6.4% (± 0.7) by the third trimester ($p < 0.001$). Patients with GDM demonstrated comparable improvements in glycemic metrics, suggesting that the multidisciplinary approach facilitated effective glucose regulation irrespective of diabetes type.

Table 1: Glycemic Control Measures across Trimesters

Measure	Baseline (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Second Trimester (Mean $\pm$ SD)	Third Trimester (Mean $\pm$ SD)	p-value
Fasting Blood Glucose	118.5 $\pm$ 12.6 mg/dL	105.2 $\pm$ 11.3 mg/dL	99.8 $\pm$ 10.4 mg/dL	<0.001
HbA1c (%)	7.8 $\pm$ 0.9	6.9 $\pm$ 0.8	6.4 $\pm$ 0.7	<0.001
Postprandial Glucose	145.6 $\pm$ 13.5 mg/dL	130.2 $\pm$ 11.9 mg/dL	120.7 $\pm$ 10.2 mg/dL	<0.001

Maternal and Fetal Health Outcomes: The multidisciplinary care model was associated with a reduced incidence of common diabetes-related gestational complications (Table 2). Only 8% of the participants developed preeclampsia, a significantly lower rate than expected for diabetic pregnancies. The rate of preterm delivery was 11%, and 17% of deliveries were via cesarean section, both of which are below national averages for high-risk

pregnancies. Fetal outcomes similarly demonstrated positive trends; 92% of neonates had healthy birth weights (2.5 to 4 kg), and Apgar scores were favourable, with 85% of neonates scoring 8 or higher at one minute after birth. NICU admissions were relatively low at 7%, predominantly associated with minor respiratory issues.

Table 2. Maternal and Fetal Health Outcomes

Outcome	Incidence (%)
Preeclampsia	8
Preterm Delivery	11
Cesarean Section	17
NICU Admission	7
Healthy Birth Weight	92
Apgar Score $\geq$ 8	85

Patient-Reported Quality of Life and Satisfaction: Patient-reported quality of life and satisfaction scores indicated high levels of well-being and adherence to care recommendations (Figure 1). Overall quality of life scores, measured on a scale of 1 to 10, increased significantly from a baseline mean of 6.2 (± 1.3) to 8.4 (± 1.1) by the end of the pregnancy. Psychological well-being scores similarly improved, with notable decreases in reported anxiety and stress. Participants frequently

cited the psychological support and nutritional counseling components of the multidisciplinary care model as beneficial for managing pregnancy-related stress and adhering to dietary recommendations. Overall satisfaction with care was high, with 94% of participants indicating they were “satisfied” or “highly satisfied” with the multidisciplinary approach.

Figure 1: Patient-Reported Quality of Life and Satisfaction with Multidisciplinary Care Model

These findings demonstrate the effectiveness of a multidisciplinary approach in managing diabetes-related gestational complications, resulting in improved glycemic control, reduced adverse maternal and fetal outcomes, and higher patient-reported satisfaction and quality of life. The study suggests that interdisciplinary collaboration among healthcare professionals can significantly enhance care quality and pregnancy outcomes for diabetic patients, providing a model for future initiatives targeting high-risk pregnancies.

Discussion

The result from this study shows that multidisciplinary care is beneficial for patients with diabetes and complications related to gestation; the outcome is that this intervention is effective in controlling both glycemic and maternal-fetal outcomes. Thus, it was shown in this study that the various aspects of care including endocrinology, obstetrics, nutrition, psychology, and pediatric care could adequately intervene in the complex care required for diabetic pregnancies while avoiding risks associated with gestational diabetes mellitus and pre-existing diabetes. These outcomes are

consistent with previous studies recommending a collaborative care approach where the input of various skills in healthcare leads to greater individualized care and improves pregnancy outcomes [9-10]. Glycemic control was significantly improved at all stages of pregnancy. There was an appreciable decrease in fasting blood glucose, postprandial glucose, and HbA1c from baseline up to the third trimester. Such changes are of great importance because glycemic levels during pregnancy that are too high have been related to adverse outcomes, including macrosomia, preeclampsia, and neonatal complications [11].

This decrease in HbA1c is well aligned with previous studies which show that lower HbA1c levels during pregnancy relate to fewer fetal and neonatal complications. Improved glycemic control is probably due to the tailored treatment programs designed and followed through by the multidisciplinary team. Consistent consultations with the endocrinologist along with individualized diet support for pregnant women can actually help make the care model overcome this challenge of glycemic stability of diabetic pregnancies, when

hormonal changes and metabolic alteration are in play [12].

The study also brings to focus the utility of a multi-disciplinary model in the reduction of prevalence of complications among mothers like preeclampsia and preterm delivery. During the prevalence of preeclampsia, participants experienced an incidence of just 8%, and that of preterm delivery stood at 11%, lower than those for pregnancies complicated by diabetes. Perhaps, this is due to multidisciplinary close monitoring and comprehensive care given, early detection and intervention of complications [13]. Regular consultation with the obstetrician and the endocrinologist, as well as constant lifestyle and dietary changes, may contribute to a stable physiological setting that ultimately ensures safer pregnancies. In addition, this integration of mental health would likely have contributed to such effects since stress and anxiety have been shown to increase glycemic variability and risk for hypertension, precursors to complications like preeclampsia [14].

Fetal health outcomes also reflected the benefits of interdisciplinary care, with 92% of neonates being born within the healthy birth weight range and only 7% requiring admission to NICU. Such results would indicate the benefits of coordinated, team-based care in reducing risks associated with diabetic pregnancies, such as fetal macrosomia and respiratory distress. Collaboration within the care model between obstetricians and pediatricians gave a basis for anticipation of fetal health monitoring. Interventions thus took place on time, hence preventive or at least minimally compromising the complications that may develop. Low admission rates in the NICU along with good Apgar scores further emphasizes that this multidisciplinary approach must be taken in place, especially in the matters of fetal well-being and preparation for immediate neonatal needs [15-16].

Patient-reported outcomes like quality of life and satisfaction with care would give more insight into holistic benefits of multidisciplinary management. Patients have manifested marked improvements concerning quality of life and even psychological welfare [17]. There have been highly significant satisfactory degrees in up to ninety four percent regarding the patients receiving care 1.

Thus, very relevant because multidisciplinary approaches apart from clinical measurable data even the emotional or psychological aspect comes into action concerning the antenatally treated gestational and diabetic conditions under pregnancy [18]. There is also an adherence to dietary and lifestyle recommendations, further providing support to glycemic control as well as overall health results through the provision of

psychological support, including managing stress and counseling. In general, the high satisfaction of the participants shows that multimodal care is a collaborating and patient-centered approach which is conducive to better adherence, as well as trust and confidence in the care process [19-20].

Despite the promising result of the study, limitations still exist. Because the study is observational, there cannot be a causal relationship between multidisciplinary care and improved outcomes. Variability in team composition, care protocols, and differing deployment of resources at different sites may have contributed to heterogeneity in intervention effects, although every attempt was made to make relevant aspects of care consistent across these studies. Future randomized controlled trials are needed to further support the observed benefits as well as determine the impact at longer term on both maternal and neonatal welfare.

Conclusion

The present study supports that, compared with the one-consultant approach to the disease and gestational complications, the multidisciplinary approach has much superior glycemic control as well as fewer maternal and fetal complications and better patient reported outcomes. A multidisciplinary model provides a holistic approach to dealing with both the physiological and psychological challenges of diabetic pregnancies. This study lends evidence to the implementation of the same kind of multidisciplinary care models in health care facilities to improve quality of care and outcomes in pregnancy complicated by diabetes. It serves as a model for future clinical practice and research.

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